

TITLE

Bibliometric Analysis of Attitudes towards Intimate Partner Violence against Women: A Study Protocol

AUTHORS

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KEYWORDS

Beliefs, Perceptions, Domestic Violence, Violence against Women, Brain, Systematic review

INTRODUCTION

Intimate partner violence against women (IPVAW) is one of the most prevalent forms of violence against women, representing a severe public health concern that affects around 30% of women worldwide, with up to 753 million victims (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023). IPVAW includes any form of violence exerted over women by a current or former male intimate partner, resulting in significant short and long-term sequelae (Bryst & Fausto, 2021). Although notable progress has been made through the implementation of policies aimed at reducing IPVAW, its prevalence remains unacceptable, and a deeper understanding of its causes is essential to enhance intervention and prevention efforts (Istanbul convention, 2014).

Attitudes towards IPVAW have been demonstrated to be crucial in predicting its perpetration (Serrano-Montilla et al., 2020). These attitudes encompass long-term standing evaluation of IPVAW, including a wide-range of beliefs about both the acts of violence, the perpetrators and the victims (Herrero et al., 2017). At an interpersonal level, attitudes that tolerate or legitimise IPVAW have been related to current perpetration (Guerrero-Molina et al., 2021). At a macro level, attitudes supporting violence influence help-seeking among victims, their environment, responses from judicial systems, support institutions and ultimately, IPVAW prevalence (Heise et al., 2015). Therefore, challenging and changing attitudes that tolerate and justify IPVAW has become an essential step for prevention policies.

Over the past few years, interest in studying attitudes toward IPVAW has grown significantly (Lila et al., 2020). The literature has primarily focused on two areas: first, the direct examination of these attitudes through the development of questionnaires (e.g., Martín-Fernández et al., 2018) or intervention programs aimed at changing them (WHO, 2019); and second, using these attitudes as explanatory variables for IPVAW perpetration (Gracia et al., 2023), or, in some cases, to explain other social phenomena (Zegeye et al., 2022). Much of this research has been compiled in systematic reviews (Gracia et al., 2020; Villagran et al., 2024; Zark et al., 2022), which highlight the lack of conceptual convergence (i.e. lack of agreement on how to define and categorize different types of attitudes) and the limited exchange of knowledge and international collaboration in addressing these attitudes.

In addition, when exploring the fields that study attitudes toward IPVAW, most research has been conducted in sociology, politics, and psychology. Recently, neuroscience has played a greater role in supporting a multidisciplinary approach, providing valuable insights into the neural mechanisms underlying these attitudes (Amaoui et al., 2022; Marín-Morales et al., 2022). Despite this growing

interest, the full extent of neuroscience's impact on the field remains unclear, and further research is needed to explore its potential contributions.

In this sense, bibliometric analysis can play a pivotal role in offering valuable knowledge into the current state of attitudes towards IPVAW and the emerging neuroscientific field to the topic. Bibliometric analysis is a quantitative method used to explore large volumes of scientific literature (Donthu et al., 2021). It involves techniques such as co-occurrence analysis, social network analysis, and cluster analysis to summarize the evolution of a particular discipline, identify research gaps, trends, and highlight emerging areas of focus (Sweileh et al., 2018).

Although several bibliometric studies have recently been conducted on topics related to attitudes towards IPVAW, such as gender inequality (Nitiwatthana & Prabpala, 2024), domestic violence (Trivedi et al., 2022), family violence (Basilio et al., 2021), and general violence against women (Bracho-Fuenmayor et al., 2024; Tavassoli et al., 2022), only one study has closely approached the field of attitudes (Badenes-Sastre & Expósito, 2021). This bibliometric study, specifically focuses on mapping the literature regarding the perception and detection of violence against women and self-identification as victims of gender violence. Although the study provided invaluable insights, it does not include key terms such as 'attitudes' or 'beliefs,' which would offer a more comprehensive view of the scientific work on the topic. Additionally, it overlooks other types of violence, such as domestic violence and partner violence, which are terms that are often used interchangeably for IPVAW. Given these limitations and considering that the previous studies did not specifically aim to examine attitudes towards IPVAW, the present study will be the first attempt to map this field through a bibliometric analysis.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Provide an overview of the state-of-the-art research literature on attitudes towards IPVAW.

Specific objectives (SO):

- SO1.** Identify the research trend of scientific publications in attitudes towards IPVAW.
- SO2.** Analyse the impact and productivity of authors and journals engaged in attitudes towards IPVAW.
- SO3.** Disclose the highly cited studies in the field.
- SO4.** Identify the countries that contribute the most to attitudes towards IPVAW research and to analyse the collaboration network among these countries.
- SO5.** Analyse the cluster network of keyword co-occurrence within the topic.
- SO6.** Examine the thematic evolution of attitudes towards IPVAW.
- SO7.** Examine whether neuroscience is one of the emerging research themes in attitudes towards IPVAW research.

METHODS

Inclusion criteria

The present study will follow the PCC (Population/Concept/Context) framework recommended by Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI; Aromataris et al., 2014):

Population

Considering the broad scope of the topics and the aim of providing a comprehensive overview of the research literature, no restrictions will be applied to the characteristics of the participants. There will be no limitations on sociodemographic factors, history of experiencing or perpetrating IPVAW, or any other related variables.

Concept

Three main concept composes the present article:

1. Intimate partner violence against women (IPVAW)

IPVAW (Intimate Partner Violence Against Women) is defined as any form of violence against women exerted by a current or former male intimate partner, regardless of whether they cohabit. According to the WHO (2019), there are four main forms of expression:

- a. *Physical violence*, which includes actions that directly or indirectly cause physical harm.
- b. *Sexual violence*, encompassing any act that violates sexual freedom and integrity.
- c. *Psychological violence*, which refers to aggression that harms a woman's mental and emotional health through behaviours like humiliation, insults, and threats, both in private and public contexts.
- d. *Controlling behaviours*, such as isolating the person and restricting access to financial resources, education, employment, and medical care.

Within the category of controlling behaviours, we will focus separately on:

- e. *Economic violence*, which includes any act or behaviour causing economic harm, such as economic control, exploitation, and sabotage (Costa, 2023).
- f. *Technology-facilitated violence* refers to any violent act committed, instigated, or aggravated through information and communication technologies (WHO, 2023).

Beyond the forms of violence already discussed, this study will also examine:

- g. *Vicarious violence*, which involves threatening or inflicting physical or psychological harm on the emotional surroundings of the woman (e.g., children), with the intent to hurt her.
- h. *Institutionalized violence*, which is any action or omission by authorities, public personnel, or agents of public institutions that delays, obstructs, or prevents access to public policies and the exercise of rights recognized by law.
- i. *Femicides*, defined as the killing of women because of their gender, specifically focusing on those perpetrated by a male intimate partner.

2. Attitudes

Attitudes will be defined as a person's long-term beliefs, or evaluations toward a particular object, person, event, or idea (Vogel & Wanke, 2016). Attitudes are typically expressed through thoughts,

emotions, and behaviours and can influence how individuals perceive and respond to the world around them. For the present study, we will use the attitudes' model proposed by Lila et al. (2020):

DIMENSIONS	LEGITIMATION	ACCEPTABILITY	ATTITUDES TOWARD INTERVENTION	PERCEIVED SEVERITY
CATEGORIES	Victim-blaming	Acceptability/ acceptance	Willingness to act/help/intervene	Perceived severity
	Justification	Approval	Attitudes towards policing, law	Perceived seriousness
	Legitimation	Permissive attitudes	Attitudes towards reporting	Minimization
	Sympathy for women victims	Tolerance	Propensity to intervene	Perception as abuse
	Attribution of responsibility to victim		Solutions involving public authorities vs family and friends	Recognition
	Stigma towards survivors*		Helping intentions towards victims	

* Stigma towards survivors will be included in the legitimation dimension, even though it was not part of the original model.

3. Measure

In the present study we will include any type of measure assessing attitudes towards IPVAV. That is:

- Self-report: a full questionnaire or subscale.
- Survey-based: large-scale population surveys such as national surveys, that assess general attitudes toward IPVAV.
- Behavioural: a task-based measure of attitudes towards IPVAV.
- Physiological: measures of physiological responses (e.g., heart rate, skin conductance) to stimuli related to IPVAV.
- Neural measures: neuroimaging techniques, such as fMRI or EEG, to assess brain activity in relation to attitudes towards IPVAV stimuli.

Context

No exclusion criteria will be applied for context assessments. The review will include studies conducted within various contexts, including community (general population), clinical settings and/or institutional environments (such as schools, workplaces or prisons).

Type of sources

Only peer-reviewed articles will be considered for the study, including both quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method studies. Specifically, the review will encompass: (a) **observational studies**, including prospective or retrospective cohort studies, cross-sectional studies, and case-control studies; (b) **experimental** and **quasi-experimental** studies, such as randomized controlled trials and non-randomized controlled trials; (c) **Qualitative** studies, including interviews, focus groups, and ethnographic research (d) **Systematic reviews** and **meta-analyses** related to the topic. Gray literature (e.g., conference abstracts, PhD and master's thesis), opinion articles, book chapters, letters to the editor will be excluded. Only records available in English will be considered eligible for inclusion.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology will follow three main steps: Search Strategy, Source of Evidence Selection, and Bibliometric Analysis

Search Strategy

1. Developing the search query

The search strategy which will be organized into two key components. The first component will focus on the topic of IPVAW while the second one will address the concept of attitudes. Keywords were identified by reviewing five recent systematic reviews on the topic (Villagrán et al., 2024; García-Cuellar et al., 2023; Mojahed et al., 2022; Badenes-Sastre et al., 2024; Bacchus et al., 2024). These reviews, published between 2022 and 2025, were conducted by different authors across diverse cultures and countries, ensuring a more comprehensive search. The final keywords are as follows:

COMPONENT	KEYWORDS
Intimate Partner Violence against Women	intimate partner violen* OR intimate partner abus* OR intimate violen* OR intimate terroris* OR partner abus* OR partner aggress* OR partner violen* OR domestic violen* OR domestic abus* OR domestic violen* offen* OR domestic offen* OR spous* abus* OR spous* violen* OR battere* OR violen* between partner* OR violen* against wom* OR violen* relation* OR marital violen* OR marital abus* OR dating violen* OR wife abus* OR wife beat* OR wives abus* OR wives beat* OR husband* abus* OR abus* relation* OR famil* violen* OR relation* abus* OR relation* violen* OR relation* aggress* OR couple violen* OR marital rape OR abused wom* OR abused spous* OR abused partner* OR abused wife OR abused wives OR interparent* violen* OR conjugal violen* OR gender-based violen* OR gender violen* OR gender-related violen* OR femicide* OR gender-based kill* OR wife murder* OR wives murder* OR intimate partner homicide* OR honor kill* OR dowry death*
Attitudes	attitud* OR opinion* OR prejudi* OR attribut* OR belie* OR accept* OR percept* OR reject* OR approv* OR blam* OR stereotyp* OR justif* OR legitim* OR responsib* OR tolera* OR willing* OR propensi* OR intent* to act OR intent to interven* OR intent to hel* OR intent to repor* perce* OR perceive* sever* OR perceive* seriousness OR perceive* gravit* OR percept* gravit* OR minimi* OR sexis* OR view OR thought* OR bias* OR stigma* OR disapprov* OR social norm* OR moral* OR misogyn* OR myth* OR stereotyp*

2. Implementing the search query

The search query will be adapted to the selected database. We will use Scopus as the main database for several reasons: (a) it provides a comprehensive overview of global research output across different disciplines and cover a high percent of other databases publications (Adriaanse & Rensleigh, 2013); (b) Scopus also includes non-English content, as long as an English title and abstract, references in Roman script, are available. Therefore, by limiting the search to English, we are including all the studies available in Scopus (Baas et al., 2020); (c) Among the five systematic reviews consulted for the search query, Scopus, along with PubMed and Web of Science, were the most commonly used databases. However, Scopus is considered the most comprehensive of these options. While PubMed primarily focuses on life sciences and biomedical disciplines (AlRyalat et al., 2019), Scopus offers broader coverage. In addition, it includes nearly all the journals indexed in Web of Science and also features a larger number of exclusive journals, except for the fields of natural sciences and engineering (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2015). This was also verified in a preliminary search for this study, where Scopus yielded the highest number of studies (23,272 studies compared to 21,120).

The search will be performed for title, abstract and keywords and will not be restricted by region, or publication time frame. Studies will be limited to English and peer-reviewed (Articles and Reviews). The final search query will be:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("intimate partner violen*" OR "intimate partner abus*" OR "intimate violen*" OR "intimate terroris*" OR "partner abus*" OR "partner aggress*" OR "partner violen*" OR "domestic violen*" OR "domestic abus*" OR "domestic violen* offen*" OR "domestic offen*" OR "spous* abus*" OR "spous* violen*" OR battere* OR "violen* between partner*" OR "violen* against wom*" OR "violen* relation*" OR "marital violen*" OR "marital abus*" OR "dating violen*" OR "wife abus*" OR "wife beat*" OR "husband* abus*" OR "abus* relation*" OR "famil* violen*" OR "relation* abus*" OR "relation* violen*" OR "relation* aggress*" OR "couple violen*" OR "marital rape" OR "abused wom*" OR "abused spous*" OR "abused partner*" OR "abused wife" OR "abused wives" OR "interparent* violen*" OR "controlling relation*" OR "conjugal violen*" OR "gender-based violen*" OR "gender violen*" OR "gender-related violen*" OR "femicide*" OR "gender-based kill*" OR "wife murder*" OR "wives murder*" OR "intimate partner homicide*" OR "honor kill*" OR "dowry death*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (attitud* OR opinion* OR prejudi* OR attribut* OR belie* OR accept* OR percept* OR reject* OR approv* OR blam* OR stereotyp* OR justif* OR legitim* OR responsib* OR tolera* OR willing* OR propensi* OR "intent* to act" OR "intent to interven*" OR "intent to hel*" OR "intent to repor*" OR perce* OR "perceive* sever*" OR "perceive* seriousness" OR "perceive* gravit*" OR "percept* gravit*" OR minimi* OR sexis* OR view OR thought* OR bias* OR stigma* OR disapprov* OR "social norm*" OR "moral*" OR "misogyn*" OR "myth*" OR "stereotyp*") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

Study/Source of Evidence Selection

To verify whether the search query yields correct eligible studies, we will check if the first 20 studies include the keywords and we will ensure that at least 10 previously selected eligible studies are part of the resulting search.

After the previous verification step, studies will be exported in RIS format for duplicate removal in *Rayyan* and in BibTex format for the bibliometric analysis. All information will be exported for each study:

- Citation information
- Bibliographical information
- Abstract & keywords
- Funding details
- Other information

Studies in RIS format will be imported into *Rayyan* (<https://www.rayyan.ai/>) to remove duplicates. First, the automatic tool with a 95% similarity threshold will be used, and any remaining duplicates will be removed manually. Below this threshold, false positives may appear.

The remaining records will be exported in CSV format and imported into *asreview lab* (<https://asreview.nl/>). This step is crucial, as it ensures that the selected studies are indeed relevant to the topic of interest. *asreview* is an open-source, machine learning—based software design to assist in systematic reviews (Boetje & van de Shoot, 2024). The tool uses an active learning approach, where the system suggests studies to review based on the researcher's input (i.e., records are labelled as relevant or irrelevant), continuously learning from each decision made to improve the selection process. This method considerably decreases the time needed for screening large datasets, enhances the transparency of the decision-making process, and minimizes the likelihood of bias, thereby ensuring a more reliable and robust review process (Khalil et al., 2022; Roth et al., 2023). In the present study we will implement the Oracle mode with default settings to screen the dataset (Ferdinands et al., 2020; Van De Schoot et al., 2021). The classification of the articles as relevant or irrelevant will follow a decision flowchart:

1. Screening step:

Due to the large number of expected articles, this step will be carried out by two independent reviewers (SA and MDSR). The dataset will be divided into two parts, with studies randomized to avoid any bias in the division due to the order of publication. Both reviewers are experienced in the field of IPVAW and will be trained to use the flowchart decision tree.

During the screening process, articles will be directly included if (a) the title or abstract explicitly states that the study measures or targets attitudes toward IPVAW (e.g., an intervention program). Articles that do not meet this criterion will be considered eligible for full-text review if they: (a) include a measure of attitudes, or (b) target attitudes (e.g., in the case of intervention programs).

2. Categorization step:

Based on a pilot, study will be divided into the following topics:

- Study Type 1. Attitudes Towards IPVAW: this category will encompass articles that create or validate measures, as well as studies where the main objective involves attitudes towards IPVAW (e.g., the development of a measure, surveys, or interventions aimed at changing attitudes).
- Study Type 2. IPVAW Experiences: will focus on articles that examine IPVAW experiences or situations and include attitudes towards IPVAW as a variable of interest.

- Study Type 3. Related to IPVAW. will include studies that focus on topics closely related to IPVAW (i.e., gender inequality, Patriarchal beliefs, women empowerment, sexism, women autonomy, masculinity).
- Study Type 4. Other Forms of Violence or attitudes towards other types of violence: will include any study that focuses on other forms of violence (e.g., childhood violence, gender-based violence, violence against women, or mixed forms of violence) but also assesses attitudes towards IPVAW)
- Study Type 5. Not Related to Any Form of Violence: will include articles that focus on topics not related to violence (e.g., childhood diarrhea, contraception, fertility, mental health) but measure attitudes towards IPVAW.

If an article does not fit into any of the previous classifications, or if the reviewers identify a substantial number of studies that could fit into a new grouping, a new category will be created.

As recommended by the JBI guidelines (Peters et al., 2020), a **pilot test** will be conducted before starting the screening process to assess the implementation of the flowchart: (1) An expert will retrieve 200 studies, ensuring that 60 of these studies are eligible and cover a range of topics. (2) SA and MDSR will screen the titles and abstracts using the decision tree. (3) Both reviewers will meet to resolve any discrepancies, make necessary adjustments to the flowchart, and calculate the agreement rate. Cohen's Kappa statistic will be used to measure agreement, and the formal process will only begin once a Kappa score greater than 0.8 is achieved.

Final eligible studies will be imported to bibliometrix under R in Bibtext format to run the main bibliometric analysis.

Bibliometric analysis

For the bibliometric analysis, we will use the Bibliometrix open-source R package and VOSviewer. Both tools allow researchers to analyze and visualize publication data. The Bibliometrix R package will be used for comprehensive science mapping, while VOSviewer will be utilized for visualization mapping.

RESULTS' PRESENTATION

Each of the specific objective will be answered independently:

SO1. Identify the research trend of scientific publications in attitudes towards IPVAW.

The tool will generate a graph showing annual scientific production. A description of the results will be provided, followed by a discussion of the increasing interest in studying attitudes toward IPVAW in recent years.

SO2. Analyse the impact and productivity of authors and journals engaged in attitudes towards IPVAW.

To identify the journals with the greatest impact on the topic, we will present a table of the top 20 journals, ranked according to three key metrics calculated by Bibliometrix: the h-index, g-index, and total citations. For authors, a graph will be included displaying the 10 most productive authors over time. A summary of the results will be included.

SO3. Disclose the highly cited studies in the field.

Bibliometrix will use the reference lists to rank the 20 most cited studies in attitudes toward IPVAW research. We will focus on two key metrics: total citations and total citations per year.

SO4. Identify the countries that contribute the most to attitudes towards IPVAW research and analyse the collaboration network among these countries.

To identify the number of articles per country, Bibliometrix will use the authors' country affiliations. Additionally, we will examine country-specific production over time to assess any shifts in research interest. For the collaboration network, Bibliometrix will use the MCP variable, which indicates the number of documents in which at least one co-author is from a different country. A network graph will be generated to visualize the international collaboration between countries.

SO5. Analyse the cluster network of keyword co-occurrence within the topic.

The co-occurrence of keywords is evaluated to determine the cluster network for a given field of study. Before running the cluster analysis, we will check the top author keywords by occurrences. If trivial terms are identified, they will be removed. Additionally, synonyms, plural forms, or different conjugations of the same term will be combined to ensure consistency and accuracy in the analysis.

For the network analysis, we will use the most common graphs to represent co-occurrence: the first will be a network map, and the second will be a density map of the keywords, both created using VOSviewer software.

SO6. Examine the thematic evolution of attitudes towards IPVAW

The thematic evolution analysis will be based on co-word network analysis and clustering. In this study, an alluvial diagram will be conducted to assess the thematic evolution within the field of attitudes towards IPVAW. A description of the results will be done by dividing the timeline into periods. However, these periods will be decided depending on the results.

SO7. Examine whether neuroscience is one of the emerging research themes in attitudes towards IPVAW research.

A strategic diagram, defined as a two-dimensional structure will be plotted in accordance with the centrality and density rank values (Martínez-Martínez et al., 2022). The strategies diagram is divided into four quadrants:

- *Motor themes*: These themes are well-established and play a key role in shaping the structure of a research field (high levels of both centrality and density).
- *Niche themes*: These themes have solid internal connections but limited external links, making them relatively minor in regional importance.
- *Emerging or declining themes*: These themes are underdeveloped and marginal, and usually are the declining or emerging topics within the field (low centrality and density).
- *Basic and transversal themes*: These themes are important to the research area but are still in the early stages of development.

We expect to find **neuroscience** (or any related word) within the *Emerging themes* or as a *Basic and transversal theme*.

LIMITATIONS

We acknowledge that the study will have some limitations. While we have carefully selected the database for this research, we recognize that some studies not indexed in Scopus will be overlooked.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing interest.

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